

Linking physical processes to biological responses: Interdisciplinary observational insights into the enhanced biological productivity of the Cape Verde Archipelago[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The Cape Verde Archipelago (CVA) is a hotspot of biological productivity in the oligotrophic central North Atlantic, supporting a highly diverse ecosystem. Twenty years of interdisciplinary observational data are used to investigate the primary physical processes driving this productivity and their impacts on the composition of biological life across the food web of the CVA. Three dominant physical processes are identified: **I. Atmospheric forced island wakes:** Wind interactions with the topography of Santo Antão and Fogo generate local wind shear, creating surface-intensified, productive eddy fields that extend several island diameters downstream. **II. Interaction of remotely generated mesoscale eddies with the CVA:** Nitrate-rich eddies generated off the coast of West Africa interact with the CVA by colliding with the eastern islands, or by passing near shallow bathymetry. This interaction enhances submesoscale activity, likely driven by unbalanced mesoscale flow, leading to hotspots of vertical advection and mixing. Our observations indicate, in addition, interactions between passing eddies and island-induced processes, such as an elevated internal wave field and wind curl in lee of the islands. This results in up to a tenfold increase in mixing within near-island eddies. **III. Interactions of tidal flows and internal waves with the CVA:** Internal wave breaking at specific hotspots, such as south of Santo Antão, leads to elevated vertical mixing rates, up to 1000 times higher than at reference points. The mean internal wave field in the CVA is over twice as energetic as in the open ocean, and even stronger at distinct hotspots. These three physical processes, although different in nature, all enhance upward nitrate flux, thereby promoting significantly higher chlorophyll concentrations. This, in turn, forms the foundation of the local pelagic food web, including mesozooplankton and micronekton, such as mesopelagic fishes, whose abundance increase three- to tenfold at these local hotspots. The composition of the biological communities is highly diverse and varies across different regions and physical processes. Annual landings of mackerel and tuna on the CVA, as well as the abundance of humpback whales, are positively correlated with annual mean chlorophyll concentrations. Overall, our study reveals a strong correlation between nitrate supply to the euphotic zone, driven by various physical processes, and species abundance throughout the food web, extending to large predators. These findings underscore the crucial role of local physical processes in shaping the structure of marine communities from lower to higher trophic levels, explaining biological diversity in the marine environment of the CVA and beyond.

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1. Introduction

The state of the ocean, encompassing both its circulation and the marine ecosystem on a large scale, is intricately connected to and partially governed by small-scale physical processes of vertical exchange (e.g. De Falco et al., 2022). Over the past decades, numerous studies have focused on these linkages, elucidating the underlying individual physical processes (e.g. Ledwell et al., 2000; Lévy et al., 2018; Moum et al., 2002; Polzin et al., 1997). These physically driven vertical exchange processes, particularly vertical advection and mixing, influence not only the physical characteristics of the ocean but also impact biogeochemical characteristics, such as carbon uptake, oxygen concentration or nutrient availability (e.g. Brandt et al., 2015; Karstensen et al., 2017; Lévy et al., 2012; Schütte et al., 2016b; Thomsen et al., 2016). These characteristics, in turn, directly influence biological processes including primary production, vertical migration, distribution and abundance of different species (e.g. Bakun & Weeks, 2006; Hummels et al., 2020; Karstensen et al., 2015; Stenvers et al., 2021). The exact mechanisms, feedbacks and cascades that underly the interaction between ocean physics, biogeochemistry, biology and even fisheries are unknown for many ocean regions and require an integrated observational and local high-resolution approach.

Vertical exchange is strongly amplified near islands, the coast or over areas with steep and rough topography such as seamounts (e.g. Brandt et al., 2015; Körner et al., 2024; Ledwell et al., 2000; Moum et al., 2002; Schafstall et al., 2010). When this physical forcing is aligned with a vertical nutrient gradient, it facilitates upward nutrient fluxes, leading to enhanced primary productivity, an increase in local plankton biomass, and potentially higher trophic levels. This cascading effect of physical, biogeochemical and biological events ultimately causes increased productivity in the vicinity of islands and is thus a major component of the “Island-Mass Effect” (IME), which was characterized by Doty and Oguri (1956). The elevated biological productivity associated with the IME makes offshore islands ecologically prominent areas in an otherwise oligotrophic ocean (e.g. Gove et al., 2016). This led to numerous studies on various processes around islands that contribute to the IME (e.g. De Falco et al., 2022). In the literature, the IME is mainly explained by one or a combination of the following five processes. First, a large-scale flow around an island may generate eddy fields or so-called ‘island wakes’ which can extend for several island diameters downstream (Barton, 2001). Second, wind distortions by the island’s topography cause, e.g., local wind stress curl and result in upward/downward Ekman pumping, which can generate two stationary eddies in the lee of an island (Caldeira et al., 2014), or local upwelling (in this context a combination of vertical advection and mixing) due to the alignment of coastline and wind direction (Kämpf, 2024). Third, a geostrophic flow and an Ekman drift can interact with an island’s bathymetry to produce a vertical flux of nutrients (Hasegawa et al., 2004). Fourth, tide-topography interactions around the island act like a stirring rod, intensifying the internal wave field and enhancing vertical mixing (Wyatt et al., 2020). Fifth, freshwater runoff from the islands delivers nutrients nearshore (Gove et al., 2016). Although all these rather small-scale physical processes are local phenomena, they occur similarly in many locations in the world ocean and the combined effects have been shown to be important for chlorophyll (CHL) distribution at basin and global scale (Gove et al., 2016). However, most of the studies analyzing such physical processes focus on single processes over large ocean areas instead of focusing comprehensively on several processes on a small geographical scale, such as a specific archipelago or island.

The Cape Verde Archipelago (CVA) and its associated seamounts are located offshore (600–900 km off the West African coast) in the eastern tropical North Atlantic. Near the West African coast, surface waters are influenced by coastal upwelling (most pronounced usually in boreal spring) (Mittelstaedt, 1983; Wooster et al., 1976). This is visible in satellite images by reduced sea surface temperature and enhanced CHL. This region is associated with high biological productivity from

phytoplankton and zooplankton up to higher trophic levels (Lachkar & Gruber, 2012; Messie et al., 2009). In the subsurface layers (aphotic zone), nitrate is reaccumulated in inorganic form through the remineralization of sinking organic matter. Further offshore, where the effect of upwelling diminishes, nitrate availability and consequently primary productivity is in general limited. Within this biologically less productive, nitrate-limited, open ocean region (Moore et al., 2013), the CVA stands out as a hotspot of biological productivity and marine life (Hoving et al., 2020; Stenvers et al., 2021). Traditionally, the primary source of productivity enhancement in the CVA is attributed to the seasonal coastal upwelling along the West African coast, which sometimes extends west up to the CVA through horizontal advection of filaments or currents (Fernandes et al., 2005; Lathuilière et al., 2008). However, observations from decades of satellite-derived chlorophyll data reveal a decoupled seasonal cycle of CHL in the CVA region and the coastal upwelling system off West Africa (Fig. 1b or supplementary materials Fig. S1). This indicates that direct lateral mean or eddy advection of biomass does not play a major role in the primary production of the CVA.

The increased CHL concentration in the CVA provides basic energetic resources for the higher trophic levels which in turn support national fisheries as well as international fishing fleets. While the IME has historically been associated with enhanced CHL, there is clear evidence that the increased primary productivity propagates to higher trophic levels by influencing the distribution of primary and secondary consumers (Randelhoff et al., 2020; Yamazaki & Kawahata, 1998). The population of large predators is occasionally increased near seamounts and islands (Boehlert & Genin, 1987), sustaining commercial fishing and also associated tourism. However, it is not straightforward to determine the relative role of an enhanced pelagic food web in comparison to the structure and prey availability that the benthic habitats of the island slopes provide. The few examples of the IME in the Atlantic Ocean show enhanced mesozooplankton and gelatinous zooplankton abundance leeward of islands off Brazil and the Canary Islands (Hernández-León, 1991; Salvetat et al., 2022). However, quantitative measurements of the abundance of mesopelagic micronekton and macrozooplankton in relation to the IME are virtually absent (for the Atlantic) to our knowledge, although these taxa sustain a high diversity in the CVA (Hoving et al., 2020), abundance (Christiansen et al., 2018) and an enormous biomass (Stenvers et al., 2021).

This study endeavors to approach a comprehensive understanding of the interdisciplinary connections around the CVA through the combination of a variety of observational physical, biogeochemical and biological datasets collected over many years. The enhanced primary production of the CVA and the underlying physical processes are characterized in detail for the first time, shedding light on the connection between physical processes and their role for the local ecosystem of the archipelago. We hypothesize that small-scale local physical processes around the islands lead to an increased nitrate flux into the mixed layer, which promotes regional CHL blooms and ultimately support a rich and diverse ecosystem.

This study is structured as follows: At first, the data and methods are introduced (section 2) before presenting the results and discussion of the physical forcing mechanisms (section 3) including: the general wind field and ocean circulation around and within the CVA (section 3.1), physical processes increasing primary production such as orographically induced wind stress perturbations observed near the island Fogo (3.2.1), interactions with remotely generated geostrophic flows (i.e. eddies) with the CVA (3.2.2) as well as the role of tides and internal waves (3.2.3). Then we present results and discussion on the implications of all these physical processes for the distribution of biogeochemical properties, the local ecosystem as well as specific individual foodweb components in section 4. The study is completed by a summary and conclusion (section 5).

Fig. 1. a) 23-year mean of daily CHL concentrations (2000–2022) within the CVA with a small inset map in the top right corner to show the location of the CVA in the Atlantic Ocean. b) Climatologies of 23 years of daily CHL concentrations within the CVA (median values of the red dotted box shown in a) as green line) contrasted with the median values of the box 14.5° N to 17.5° N and 16° W to 22.5° W east of the CVA (gray line). Shadings indicate the interquartile range (i.e. 25 % and 75 % percentiles of the spatial averaging). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2. Data and methods

The basis for this study consists of various interdisciplinary datasets, which are described in more detail below, conducted over the past decades during a large number of field campaigns with different objectives.

2.1. Cape Verde Atmospheric Observatory

The Cape Verde Atmospheric Observatory (CVAO) located on an exposed rocky coastline near Calhau at the northeastern tip of the island of São Vicente (position: 16° 51.82' N, 24° 52.03' W) is in operation since 2007. Wind measurements were collected at different heights at 1 Hz and then averaged over 1 min and 10 min (Carpenter et al., 2011). In this study, wind data taken 7.5 m above sea level at a temporal resolution of

1 min between October 2006 and December 2022 were used.

2.2. Slocum glider data

Segments of 12 Slocum glider missions (between 2008 and 2015) conducted south of Santo Antão are used (brown tracks in Fig. 2b). The gliders were deployed from the Ocean Science Centre Mindelo (São Vicente) to investigate open ocean mesoscale eddies or the upwelling area off the coast of Africa. On their way to the target area, they circumvented Santo Antão in the south and mostly traversed the CVA around 18°N to the east. The temperature and salinity measurements of the Gliders near the islands are used for an exemplary section and a spectral analysis of vertical displacements. A detailed description of the processing and calibration of the GEOMAR Slocum Glider is presented in Thomsen et al. (2016).

Fig. 2. a) Tracks of all 34 research cruises in the CVA used in the manuscript (in green). b) Zoom on tracks of research cruises around Santo Antão and São Vicente. Especially highlighted are the cruises in February 2018 and February 2022 (in red) as their datasets are used most intensively. The brown tracks indicate the used glider segments and the blue diamond's indicate microstructure profiles. c) Zoom on tracks of research cruises southwest of Fogo. Blue diamond's indicate microstructure profiles used in this study. Especially highlighted is a cruise in February 2019 (red). CTD profiles taken during that cruise are marked by yellow circles. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2.3. Ship-based data

The used database consists of 27 research cruises between 2003 and 2022 carried out by the GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for ocean research Kiel in the eastern tropical North Atlantic (Fig. 2a, and see table S1 supplementary materials). In addition, data from 7 cruises of the Prediction and Research Moored Array in the Tropical Atlantic (PIRATA) multinational program (Bourlès et al., 2019) led by the United States (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) crossing the CVA are used (see table 1 S1). For most of the in total 34 cruises, the starting or ending harbor was Mindelo on the Cape Verdean Island of São Vicente. Consequently, data is available within the CVA even though the research focus of the research cruises might not have been specifically dedicated to the CVA.

2.3.1. Vessel mounted Acoustic Doppler current profiler (VmaDCP)

During the cruises, underway horizontal velocity measurements were obtained from a 38 kHz, a 75 kHz or a 350 kHz RDI Ocean Surveyor (OS) vessel mounted Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (vmADCP). The accuracy of the used 1-hr averaged vmADCP data is better than 0.02 – 0.04 m s⁻¹ (Fischer et al., 2003). All velocity data were combined to obtain an average picture of the velocity structure in the archipelago. As an example, we present one mean velocity section along 23°W through the archipelago between 12°N to 20°N. To derive this mean section, velocity data from different instruments (if available, mostly OS38 kHz and OS75 kHz) are merged for each cruise accounting for the instrument specific accuracy and resolution. The velocity data are then mapped for each cruise separately on a regular grid (0.05° latitude × 10 m depth) using a Gaussian-weighted interpolation scheme with horizontal and vertical influence [cutoff] radii of 0.05° [0.1°] latitude, and 10 m [20 m] depth, respectively. All single sections are averaged to derive the mean section along 23°W, which is smoothed again by a Gaussian filter (horizontal and vertical influence [cutoff] radii: 0.05° [0.1°] latitude, and 10 m [20 m] depth). Additionally, underway velocity measurements from seven cruises (see table 1 S1) are used to estimate vertical shear energy levels according to the method outlined in Fischer et al. (2013). During these seven cruises, horizontal velocities were measured with a OS75-kHz vmADCP configured with 100 bins of 8 m bin size. Vertical shear spectra are calculated from the filtered velocities to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. Referenced to the canonical Garret-Munk-model, these vertical shear levels can be used to parameterize dissipation rates of turbulent kinetic energy. High spectral energy corresponds to high internal wave energy. Here, vertical shear spectra were computed from 48 bins of 8 m bin size approximately covering the depth range from 150 m to 535 m depth (i. e. below the thermocline, where stratification changes are weak and their impact on spectra low).

2.3.2. Conductivity, temperature and nitrate data

Hydrographic data were acquired during the research cruises using a Seabird CTD (Conductivity, Temperature, Depth) instrument. After calibration, the data accuracies for a single research cruise are generally assumed to be better than ± 0.001 °C for temperature and ± 0.004 g kg⁻¹ for salinity. Nitrate measurements used in this study (see table 1 S1) were conducted with an OPUS sensor (TriOS GmbH) mounted on the CTD rosette. After calibration, the data accuracy of the OPUS in dynamic coastal waters is better than approximately 2 μmol l⁻¹ (for more information on the OPUS calibration and processing procedures, see Nehir et al. (2021)). Water samples for salinity and nitrate sensor calibration were obtained using water from the Niskin bottles mounted on the CTD rosette.

2.3.3. Thermosalinograph

Underway temperature and salinity measurements were conducted during the research cruises using thermosalinographs (Meteor/Poseidon: *SeaBird SBE 21*, Maria S. Merian: *SeaBird SBE 45*) with seawater drawn from the ship's inlet (Poseidon: 2 m depth, Maria S.

Merian: 6 m depth, Meteor: 5 m depth). Underway CHL measurements were conducted on the Maria S. Merian using a *Wetlabs* Fluorometer located adjacent to the thermosalinograph. On all cruises, the temperature and conductivity sensors of the thermosalinographs were calibrated using the corresponding depth values from CTD profiles taken during the cruises, resulting in an accuracy of about twice the GO-SHIP standard, which is ± 0.002 °C for temperature and ± 0.004 for salinity.

2.3.4. Microstructure profiler

Turbulence dissipation rates were derived from shipboard microstructure measurements which were frequently conducted during three research cruises in the CVA (see table 1 S1). The profiling system used was an MSS90-D profiler, manufactured by Sea & Sun Technology. The loosely-tethered profiler is optimized to sink at a rate of about 0.6 m s⁻¹. The noise levels of turbulence dissipation rates from the microstructure profiler are 5 × 10⁻¹⁰ W kg⁻¹ (Schafstall et al., 2010). For more details on data processing and calibration, see Hummels et al. (2013). In total, 31 (20) vertical microstructure profiles were conducted off Santo Antão (Fogo) from 200 m off the coast to around 12 km offshore and 27 microstructure profiles in the open ocean around the Cape Verde Ocean Observatory.

2.3.5. Biological datasets

During seven cruises in different seasons between 2012 and 2019, mesozooplankton samples were collected from vertically stratified hauls with a Hydrobios Multinet Midi (0.25 m² mouth opening, five nets, 200 μm mesh size) (see table 1 S1). Standard depth ranges were 1000–600–300–200–100–0 m. For this study, only data from the euphotic zone (upper 200 m) were used. In water depths shallower than 1000 m or during dedicated eddy surveys, these depth intervals were further subdivided. Samples were fixed in a 4 % formaldehyde seawater solution. In the laboratory, samples were split into three size fractions using sieves of 1000 μm, 500 μm and 200 μm and digitized using an Epson Perfection V750 Pro Scanner. The largest size fraction was scanned entirely, while the medium and small fraction was split to reach approximately 1000–2000 objects on the 21x30 cm scanning plate. Segmentation and calculation of image parameters was conducted using the latest Zoo-Process macro set for ImageJ (Gorsky et al., 2010). Images were then imported into Exotaxa (Picheral et al., 2017), predicted with the built-in deep learning features and validated by experts. Individual biomass was calculated using the published area to dry weight relationships for subtropical zooplankton by Lehette and Hernández-León (2009) and total integrated epipelagic biomass of copepods (mg C m⁻² in the upper 200 m depth) was used as a mesozooplankton productivity indicator.

On a cruise in February 2018, oblique Hydrobios Multinet Maxi (0.5 m² mouth opening, nine nets, 4 mm mesh size, towed at 2 kn in the upper 1000 m) were collected for macrozooplankton and micronekton and likewise fixed in 4 % formaldehyde in seawater solution. These samples were manually sorted and identified in the laboratory to species or genus level for mesopelagic fishes, and to order level for most crustaceans and gelatinous zooplankton.

Landings of commercial (industrial and artisanal) fisheries within the 12-mile zone around the islands and reported nationally from 2002 to 2022 in Cape Verde were monitored by IMar (Instituto do Mar, previously INDP, Instituto Nacional de Desenvolvimento das Pescas) and categorized into tuna species (main species contributing being skipjack, yellowfin, and frigate tuna) and small pelagics (including mackerel scad *Decapterus macarellus* and bigeye scad *Selar crumenophthalmus*), for the data see (IMar, 2023). Annual Humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*) abundance (2011–2017) was used from published data (Wenzel et al., 2020) based on capture/recapture surveys using fluke photography in the CVA. To compare the multiyear landings/sighting time series, mean annual surface CHL values were calculated in a bounding box from 14 to 17.5°N and 22–26°W from monthly Chl-a products (Aqua-MODIS Level 3, with a spatial resolution of 4 km from 2002 to 2022).

2.4. Satellite based data of CHL, wind and sea level anomaly

CHL concentrations used in the manuscript are derived from ocean colour observations with spectroradiometers and provided by Marine Copernicus (<https://marine.copernicus.eu>). The datasets used include the 4 km x 4 km resolution daily data (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00282>) for the snapshots and mean seasonality, which are cloud dependent. The interpolated daily cloud-free version of CHL, also at 4 km x 4 km resolution (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00281>), is used for the CHL seasonality Hovmöller plots and the snapshot in Fig. 8 (“eddy collision”).

Wind velocity data at 10 m above sea level, with a spatial resolution of 0.25° , were used in this study. The used Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform (CCMP) 6-hourly wind dataset is produced by Remote Sensing Systems and available for the period from Jan 01, 1992 to Dec 31, 2019. The wind stress is calculated from the wind velocity data according to Pacanowski (1987), using a constant drag coefficient of 0.0013.

Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) data with a spatial resolution of 0.25° are also provided by Marine Copernicus. Specifically, Absolute Dynamic Topography, SLA, and corresponding geostrophic velocity data derived from the SLA were considered (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00148>).

3. Physical forcing mechanisms of regional CHL blooms within the CVA

3.1. The mean wind field and ocean circulation of the CVA

The energy for vertical exchange in the upper ocean through vertical advection and mixing originates primarily from wind input and large-scale ocean circulation. The wind field is relatively stable, as the CVA is located within the northeast trade wind area (Fig. 3a). At the CVAO, an average wind speed of 6.3 m s^{-1} (with a standard deviation of $\pm 2.2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) is measured during 17 years of data. The average seasonal cycle shows stronger winds during boreal winter/spring and weaker winds during boreal summer/autumn (Fig. 3b), associated with the northernmost and southernmost position of the intertropical convergence zone, respectively.

In contrast to the steady wind field, the average ocean circulation around the CVA is highly variable, rather weak and sometimes disturbed by mesoscale eddies propagating westwards through the region. While parts of the large scale circulation surrounding the CVA have been previously described, no comprehensive description of the flow field within the CVA based on observational data sets exists. Through the combination of the velocity measurements of 34 research cruises (cruise

tracks in Fig. 2a) as well as Argo floats, drifters and satellite data, we can evaluate for the first time a detailed mean local circulation pattern around the CVA with its associated variability based on observational data (Fig. 4). In the observed area (12°N – 20°N ; 20°W – 30°W), the continuous northeast trade winds result on average in a northwestward Ekman transport (around 0–50 m deep) and a westward geostrophic flow, the North Equatorial Current. Near the islands (along 23°W , close to or intersecting Maio, Boa Vista and Sal, see Fig. 4b), the lower-frequency background flow is superimposed with higher-frequency tidal flow, which often exceeds the background flow in strength (section 3.2.3). However, on average, the residual flow of the surface waters (<100 m depth) tends to exhibit an anticyclonic rotation around the islands (Fig. 4b). Beneath the wind-influenced layer, the circulation is dominated by alternating zonal jets (westward at 11.5°N – 13.5°N ; eastward at 13.5°N – 15°N ; westward at 14.8°N – 18.5°N ; eastward at 18.5°N – 20°N). The zonal jets are disturbed by the islands of the CVA, resulting in a more complex flow field in the proximity of the archipelago and its topographic features.

The strongest zonal jet (around 0.1 – 0.15 m s^{-1} between 100–700 m depth) is an eastward flow south of the CVA, between 13.5°N – 15°N , known as the Cape Verde Current (CVC) (Pena-Izquierdo et al., 2012; Stramma et al., 2008a). Other prominent features in the average velocity section along 23°W include a distinct westward flow at around 18°N in the upper 300 m depth and a broad eastward flow north of 19°N between 200 and 700 m depth (Fig. 4b). During boreal summer, these zonal jets, particularly the CVC, are much stronger and more consistent throughout the upper 700 m compared to boreal winter, when the currents are weaker and rather sluggish. The high variability of the CVC is also evident in the high standard deviation of zonal velocity south of the archipelago (< 15°N) (Fig. 4b, grey hatches), while within the archipelago, highest variability is found within the upper 100 m, primarily due to tidal flows. North of the archipelago, variability increases again but is confined to the upper 200 m depth, likely due to propagating mesoscale eddies.

In the southern part of the CVA, previous observations of the large-scale ocean circulation (Brandt et al., 2010; Hahn et al., 2014; Pena-Izquierdo et al., 2015; Stramma et al., 2008a; Stramma et al., 2005) indicate significant flow variability between 10°N and 13°N , with eastward flow north of 12°N between 200 and 800 m, very similar to our observations (Fig. 4). Observations of ocean circulation around the CVA (12°N to 20°N) shown in literature as well as those presented here indicate that the large-scale flow is significantly influenced by alternating zonal currents. The existence of such geostrophic jets far from the equator (north of 10°N) was reported by Qiu et al. (2013a, b) for the

Fig. 3. a) Wind direction and speed at a height of 7.5 m measured at CVAO and averaged over 17 years. b) Wind speed climatology (black line) and its harmonic fit (orange line). The blue shading represents a density heatmap of wind speeds for each timestep (5 days) as a percentage, with wind speed bin sizes of 0.25 m s^{-1} . (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. a) Map of the CVA region with a schematic ocean circulation from the base of the mixed layer to 700 m depth (arrows) based on a combination of various different data sets and its variability (reddish colors, lighter colors indicate “higher”, darker colors “lower” variability, based on ship sections). The black triangle marks the position of the CVAO (data shown in Fig. 3a, b) and the black dot marks the Cape Verde Ocean Observatory (CVOO) deep sea mooring. The large-scale zonally-directed arrows shaded in blue/red (separated by dashed lines) indicate the major zonal easterly/westerly jets, which appear as a weak background flow visible across all datasets. b) Mean zonal velocity along 23°W (color shading, blue westward, red eastward) as derived from 7 research cruises between 12°N and 20°N along 23°W. Also included are areas with the standard deviation of zonal velocity larger than 0.1 m s⁻¹ (grey hatches). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

North Pacific. The vertical extent of these jets can reach down to 1000 m depth and diminishes towards the east. The most prominent of these eastward currents is found at 14°N. This current, with an eastward mean flow of around 0.1 m s⁻¹, was identified by Brandt et al. (2010); Stramma et al. (2008b) and later termed CVC by Peña-Izquierdo et al. (2015). Brandt et al. (2010) speculated that this flow might represent a recirculation around the Cape Verde Islands, but Peña-Izquierdo et al. (2015) showed using model simulations that the flow extends all the way from the western Atlantic to the African continent, resembling more closely one of the zonal jets identified by Qiu et al. (2013a, b) in the Pacific. A southern branch of the CVC is also discernible between 200 m and 800 m depth at 12°N. In the north of the CVA an eastward current is observed at approximately 18°N. We designate all these eastward flowing zonal jets as CVC system, comprising the southern (sCVC), central (CVC), and northern (nCVC) branches, as also identified by Peña-Izquierdo et al. (2015). Specifically, the eastward current at 18°N is quite coherent and has not been adequately described before. Peña-Izquierdo et al. (2015) speculated that the eastward currents at 14°N, 16°N, and 18°N likely play a significant role in the ventilation of the eastern tropical North Atlantic oxygen minimum zone. More recent results using a high-resolution forced ocean model reveal the importance of the zonal jets for the formation of the oxygen minimum zones in the eastern tropical Atlantic (Calil, 2023). The presence of these eastward

currents in our data, which transport water from the relatively oxygen-rich western Atlantic to the relatively oxygen-poor eastern Atlantic, supports this hypothesis. How far the eastward jets extend to the east possibly depending on latitude, however, remains an open question.

3.2. Observed main physical processes contributing to enhanced biological productivity within the CVA

The relatively strong and persistent winds interacting with the topographic features of the CVA may trigger oceanic processes that contribute to vertical advection and mixing. Additionally, enhanced high-frequency variability of ocean velocity, linked to mesoscale eddies and/or tides, could also lead to vertical advection and mixing. Consequently, the following analysis focuses on the wind’s role in the upper ocean in the lee of high-topography islands (3.2.1), followed by the influences of remotely generated mesoscale eddies (3.2.2) and tides (3.2.3), with a combined discussion in section 3.3.

3.2.1. Atmospheric forced island wakes

On satellite images of the CHL distribution around CVA, it is noticeable that strong primary production, characterized by rather circular CHL blooms, is regularly observed in the lee of Fogo and Santo Antão. Both islands stand out due to their topography with elevations

reaching up to 2829 m (Fogo) and 1979 m (Santo Antão). The mountains are an obstacle to the wind, producing two counter rotating wind curl cells in lee (southwest) of both islands, clearly detectable in the 28-year mean of the wind curl (Fig. 5a). There is a cyclonic rotating cell at the western and an anticyclonic rotating cell at the southern side of each island (Fig. 5a) with the wind mainly being northeasterly (Fig. 3a). The wind curl and resulting wind shear in the lee of the islands induces divergence/convergence of Ekman transport in the near-surface layer of the ocean, which is compensated by Ekman suction/pumping, i.e., upward/downward transport. The associated depression/elevation of the sea level induced by the vertical Ekman motions leads to cyclonic/anticyclonic rotating surface waters under the northwestern/southeastern shear line of the wind (Barton, 2001). If, in addition, a perturbation either by the atmospheric flow (for example a change in the vorticity injection by the atmosphere through wind pulsation) or by the oceanic flow (for example through large-scale flow or mesoscale eddies) affects these wind-forced eddies (Heywood et al., 1990), they can detach from the island (Jiménez et al., 2008). Such a detachment of eddies in the CVA is suggested by the variability maxima in the 19-year SLA record (Fig. 5b) as one SLA variability maximum is located 140 km southwest of Santo Antão and one 110 km southwest of Fogo. These regions are also characterized by peak values in the standard deviation of the curl of geostrophic velocities derived from SLA data (not shown). The highest SLA variability, indicating more and/or stronger eddies detaching from the island, is observed off Fogo, where the highest topographic elevation exists. Such eddies that form in the lee of islands and, depending on the background conditions, detach from them are also termed island wakes. As in the case of Fogo and Santo Antão, where the general ocean currents along the islands are relatively weak, it is likely that the wind curl induced by the island's topography acts as a trigger mechanism for island wake formation in the CVA.

Relying solely on satellite observations, it is impossible to distinguish between locally formed island wakes or eddies that are formed remotely, such as those generated near the West African coast, which could propagate to the lee of Fogo and produce a similar SLA signature.

However, a locally generated eddy associated with an island wake has a surface-intensified shallow core (Sangrà et al., 2007), like the island wakes in lee of Fogo described in the next paragraph with at a depth of around 20 m. This contrasts with mesoscale eddies originating from the West African coast, which have core depths of about 100 m and a much deeper-reaching eddy structure (Schütte et al., 2016a).

During a research cruise along a transect between 14.0°N, 24.5°W and 14.8°N, 28.1°W from 18 to 21 February 2019, a chain of surface intensified eddies, consisting of both, cyclonic rotating eddies (cyclones) and anticyclonic rotating eddies (anticyclones), was observed (Fig. 5c). One fully developed cyclone was identified approximately 355 km off Fogo (red circle in Fig. 5c) and another cyclone in an early stage of its development around 35 km off Fogo. The transect intersects the fully developed cyclone close to its center, as indicated by vanishing zonal and meridional velocities. Close to the presumed center, a distinct local sea surface temperature (SST) minimum is observed at 27.4°W, while SSTs generally increase with distance from the island (Fig. 5c). The sea surface salinity mirrors the SST pattern with low temperatures corresponding to high salinities, and vice versa (not shown).

Within the cyclone, between 290 km and 400 km off Fogo, the density section shows doming of isopycnals down to a depth of 400 m (only the upper 200 m are shown in Fig. 5d), with an average isopycnal displacement of 33 m, lifting also the base of the mixed layer and the nitracline. The cyclone has a radius of 44 km and therefore covers an area about three times larger than the island of Fogo (the eddy characteristics are inferred here solely from the meridional velocity component as the zonal velocity component is much smaller on the conducted transect). Eddy velocities are surface intensified, with peak rotating velocities above 0.3 m s^{-1} , measured at the uppermost available vmADCP bin at 16 m. Furthermore, the surface temperature in its core is about $0.75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ lower compared to the surrounding waters (Fig. 5c). Due to their upward bending of isopycnals, cyclones are often more productive than anticyclones, a difference that is frequently evident in their surface signature. The cyclone discussed here was sampled in February 2019 and can be tracked in satellite data prior to the ship transect with

Fig. 5. a) Spatial distribution of the mean wind stress curl anomaly (averaged over 28 years of wind stress data, spatial mean subtracted). b) Spatial distribution of the daily standard deviation of the 19-year SLA time series. c) Mean currents, averaged in the upper 100 m (arrows), and SST (color) along a section southwest of Fogo (14°N, 24.5°W to 14.8°N, 28.1°W) as derived by vmADCP and Thermosalinograph from 18 to 21 February 2019. The red circle marks the detached cyclone. d) Distribution of NO_3 as function of depth and distance to Fogo as derived from OPUS measurements at CTD stations for the same section. Superimposed are contours of potential density in kg m^{-3} (grey contours) and the mixed layer depth (dashed white line). The triangles mark locations of CTD stations. The superimposed black/red lines mark the center/edges of the cyclones according to the observed cross-section velocities. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the elevated CHL concentration in its core (Fig. 6). This cyclone was generated in the lee of Fogo in early December 2018 and detached from the island in mid-December. Over the following weeks, the cyclone propagated westward into the open ocean with an average propagation speed of 5.1 km d^{-1} , gradually slowing over time. Due to cloud cover during the first half of March, the exact end of its lifetime cannot be determined, but it is estimated to have existed 3 to 3.5 months. SST satellite data (not shown) suggest a similar lifetime. The cyclone propagated a total distance of at least 355 km. Based on the size of the CHL peak, it appears the cyclone grew in size over time while gradually losing its coherence.

These observations of an island wake in the lee of Fogo demonstrate that wind perturbations caused by islands with significant topographic features can generate surface-intensified eddies in the lee of these islands. These eddies can detach from the island and propagate into the open ocean. The presented observations suggest that such cyclonic eddies, characterized by high productivity, can be tracked via satellites using their low SST and high CHL signatures.

3.2.2. Interactions of remotely generated mesoscale eddies with the CVA

At distinct hotspots along the West African coast, mesoscale eddies are formed due to horizontal and vertical current shear induced by the coastal alongshore currents (Cardoso et al., 2020; Dilmahamad et al., 2022; Schütte et al., 2016a). These eddies enclose upwelled coastal water masses (cold, fresh and nitrate-rich South Atlantic Central Water) and transport these properties offshore towards the CVA into the more oligotrophic open ocean (Schütte et al., 2016a) by westward propagation. Interactions with the CVA can either lift up nitrate-rich water from the eddy cores to the surface layer and/or generally facilitate upward nitrate flux, both potentially leading to significant primary production.

Three types of interactions can be distinguished (Fig. 7): 1. Frontal collision, 2. Eddy passing, including interactions between eddy and shelf topography, 3. Eddy passing close to the archipelago, but without any direct “contact” with topographic features. The processes involved are challenging to capture in observations. However, data collected in the CVA provide valuable insights into the mechanisms behind these three types of interactions.

Frontal collision of eddies with the CVA

The outcome of an eddy colliding with an archipelago like the CVA depends on the bathymetry, size, and shape of the individual islands in relation to the eddy size. Satellite observations indicate an anticyclonic-

Fig. 7. Schematic of different interactions of remotely generated eddies with the CVA. Eddy 1: Frontal collision with the CVA; Eddy 2: Passing the archipelago, but interacting with the shelf topography; and Eddy 3: Passing the CVA without direct “contact” with topographic features, but indirectly impacted by, e.g., enhanced internal wave field near islands and seamounts or island-induced wind curl.

mode-water eddy (low SST, high SLA, high CHL, see Schütte et al. (2016b)) that was generated near the West African coast in June 2017 and propagated westward. By the end of December 2017, the eddy collided centrally with the CVA resulting in an extremely high CHL signal lasting for approximately 2–3 weeks (Fig. 8 or supplementary materials Fig. S3). The observed CHL concentrations even exceeded those found in the coastal upwelling area of Mauretania and were strong enough to dominate the annual mean CHL concentration for 2018 in the surrounding area.

A sensitivity study (Simmons & Nof, 2000) indicates that an obstacle must be rather large before it significantly affects an eddy, with the ratio (R) of island radius to eddy radius being crucial. The impact on the eddy becomes evident when the radius of the obstacle is larger than the eddy

Fig. 6. Generation and detachment of a cyclone in the lee of Fogo as visible in snapshots of CHL satellite data. CHL data are represented on a logarithmic scale. The red boxes mark the cyclone generated off Fogo that was sampled by a research cruise 355 km off Fogo in February 2019. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Snapshots of satellite-based sea level anomaly **a)**, **b)**, **c)** and CHL **d)**, **e)**, **f)**: for 17 September 2017 **a)**, **d)** showing an anticyclone detached from the West African coast, **b)**, **e)** on 26 December 2017 the large anticyclone collided centrally with the CVA, possibly generating several smaller eddies, and **c)**, **f)** 26 January 2018 shows the situation after the collision with some smaller eddies causing extraordinary CHL blooms, such as the highlighted cyclone north of Fogo. Black circles are intended to indicate eddies and the dashed line mark the eddy track of the large anticyclone.

radius, i.e. $R > 1$. For an eddy to actually split up into two eddies, R has to fall into the range: $1 < R < 2$. This eddy splitting also generates filaments or smaller eddies with opposite rotation around the two main eddies. The extent of secondary eddy shedding decreases again with increasing diameter of the obstacle ($R > 2$) as then the obstacle has to be considered as a wall. For the case shown above (Fig. 8), the eddy had a radius of approximately 60 km and collided near Boa Vista with the topography of the CVA. Due to the relatively uniform topography

between the eastern islands, the obstacle radius can be estimated to be around 120 km, making R close to 2. Consequently, the eddy likely has to split at least into two eddies. It appears that a cyclone (along with other eddies further north) formed within the archipelago after the collision of the larger anticyclone (Fig. 8 b,c), which induced an extraordinary CHL bloom north of Fogo (Fig. 8 f). This suggests that the theoretical predictions on the outcome of an eddy collision with an island seem reasonable.

Fig. 9. **a)** Direction and strength of upper ocean currents (red arrows) from shipboard measurements taken between 27 February 2022, 15:30 and 28 February 2022, 15:00, cutting through an anticyclone northeast of Santa Luzia, São Vicente and Santo Antão. The velocity from the vmADCP is vertically averaged in the upper 200 m. The black circles indicate the approximate boundary of the eddy, estimated from several transects through the eddy center (solid/dashed line mark the surface/subsurface boundaries, respectively). The color indicates bathymetry, taken from EMODnet. The white box indicates the zoom area for the subplots **b)** and **c)** in the direct vicinity of the islands. **b)** CHL concentrations and **c)** temperature from shipboard measurements using the thermosalinograph. The red arrows indicate the direction and strength of currents from the vmADCP in the upper 200 m. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Interactions of eddies with island shelves

When a mesoscale eddy does not collide centrally but closely passes an island, its structure and intensity can change. The eddy center may shift, and its flow near the island's bathymetry can be altered. During a research cruise in February 2022, an anticyclone was observed propagating southwestward towards the islands of Santa Luzia, São Vicente and Santo Antão. The eddy was well defined down to a depth of at least 250 m and reached azimuthal velocities of more than 0.3 m s^{-1} in the upper 100 m. In the region, where the eddy's azimuthal velocity encountered shallower water off the archipelago, CHL was increased after eddy passage (Fig. 9b).

Interestingly, increased CHL particularly occurs northeast off São Vicente, where a stronger opposing countercurrent is present near the coast (Fig. 9b). Further east, despite similar eddy velocities and bathymetry (northeast of Santa Luzia), no such strong increase in productivity is noticeable. Additionally, near-surface temperature measurements (Fig. 9c) show significantly reduced temperatures at the locations of enhanced CHL northeast off São Vicente, suggesting a hotspot of enhanced vertical mixing. There are two possible ways the eddy presence could lead to enhanced vertical flux of nitrate: 1. the eddy flow could directly interact with the topography or change internal wave field through wave-eddy interactions and potentially change the level of vertical mixing intensity or 2. The eddy can transport nitrate-rich water to the places of elevated mixing intensity, which are present due to tide-topography interactions thereby increasing the nitrate gradient and hence the vertical nitrate flux. The shipboard measurements cutting through the eddy revealed enhanced nitrate concentration of $21 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ in the eddy core at 100 m depth compared to the surrounding water at the same depth (not shown). Whether the interaction of the eddy with the topography itself causes enhanced upward nitrate flux through vertical mixing or the eddy transports nitrate-rich water into a region of generally high mixing activity due to, e.g., tide-topography interactions cannot be determined here. However, both scenarios lead to increased primary production and would not occur without the presence of an eddy closely passing the islands.

Interactions within the eddies due to island induced processes

Remotely generated eddies can also interact with the CVA even when they do not directly encounter the archipelago, but instead pass by the islands at some distance. The passing eddies can interact with various processes triggered by the archipelago, such as wind curl changes in the lee of the islands as mentioned above, with locally generated eddies, or internal waves/tides generated by tide-topography interactions. During a research cruise in November/December 2019, a cyclone southwest of Fogo was intensively sampled. The surface intensified eddy had an azimuthal velocity of more than 0.3 m s^{-1} in the upper 100 m and a surface radius of about 63 km. However, positive relative vorticity was observed down to the maximum depth range of the vmADCP of about 1200 m. These characteristics indicate that, despite being at a similar position in the lee of Fogo like the cyclone described in section 3.2.1, this eddy is not part of a typical locally generated island wake, which would be weaker and more confined to the surface. Instead, we propose that it is a coherent cyclone generated near the West African coast, propagating westward into the open ocean. Compared to two other cyclones east of the CVA, this cyclone showed significantly increased vertical mixing just below the mixed layer (Fig. 10a – turbulence dissipation rates, which are a measure of the vertical mixing strength, are 10 times larger). This results in a strongly enhanced upward nitrate flux and the observed CHL bloom (Fig. 10b). In contrast to the eddy observed north of São Vincente (discussed above), enhanced mixing is not located near the bathymetry at the eddy rim but is instead found within the eddy core located in the open ocean.

3.2.3. Interactions of tidal flows and internal waves with the CVA

Besides wind (section 3.2.1) and mesoscale eddies (section 3.2.2), tide-topography interaction potentially induces strongly enhanced upward nitrate flux in the CVA. The islands and seamounts of the CVA are located in a deep-sea basin (Cape Verde Basin) with water depths between 3000 to 4000 m. Accordingly, the volcanic islands and seamounts exhibit steep slopes. In general, the barotropic tidal flow in the deep Cape Verde Basin is dominated by meridional velocities between 0.03 and 0.05 m s^{-1} (supplementary materials Fig. S4). The major contributors to the tidal flow are the lunar and solar semidiurnal tides (M_2 and

Fig. 10. a) Average profiles of dissipation rates of turbulent kinetic energy from shipboard microstructure measurements within a cyclone near Fogo (blue; center position: $14.64^\circ\text{N } 25.04^\circ\text{W}$; Time: November 2019), north of Sal (orange; center position: $17.76^\circ\text{N } 20.45^\circ\text{W}$; Time: November 2019) and northeast of the CVA (green; center position: $18.57^\circ\text{N } 17.82^\circ\text{W}$; Time: July 2019). All microstructure profiles (29 profiles for Cyclone 1, 24 profiles for Cyclone 2, and 29 profiles for Cyclone 3) were conducted within the approximate eddy cores, with the eddy radius, r , given in the legend. b) Satellite-derived CHL, along with the approximate location of the cyclone near Fogo (Cyclone1), shown as red solid and red dashed circles corresponding to the surface and subsurface eddy boundaries, respectively, as derived from vmADCP measurements. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

S_2), with the diurnal tides being significantly smaller (Gomes et al., 2015; Siedler & Paul, 1991), as verified with the TPX09 Atlas. The islands and seamounts of the CVA act as barriers for the tidal flow and therefore channel the flow into strongly amplified currents over the shallower topography, between the islands, or around the islands/seamounts. The barotropic tides interact with the topography and generate internal tides, which can further interact with topography or disintegrate to produce smaller scale internal waves, which can break and thereby end up in turbulent motions. In a seven-day record of observed current velocity in a bay south of Santo Antão (Fig. 11), all these processes are superimposed. Semidiurnally alternating velocities between 0.3 and 0.5 m s^{-1} , with highest velocities in the upper 100 m depth clearly dominate the local current field. Similar amplitudes of semidiurnally alternating velocities are also measured off Fogo and elsewhere near islands. Note that these velocities are a factor 10 larger than those of the barotropic tide in the deep ocean around the CVA. A decomposition of the measured velocities off Santo Antão into tidal currents and residual flow reveals a northward coast-parallel residual flow of around 0.11 m s^{-1} , which indicates an anticyclonic rotation around the island. Tidal harmonic analysis following Pawlowicz et al. (2002) reveals that the M_2 tide with a period of 12.42 h per cycle and an amplitude of 0.26 m s^{-1} is dominant off Santo Antão during the observational period. Unfortunately, water velocities are not available for the entire water column. Thus, from observations, no statement can be made about the barotropic tidal component south of Santo Antão. Tidal models (e.g., TPX09, see supplementary materials Fig. S4) indicate a barotropic tidal flow south of Santo Antão of about 0.05 – 0.06 m s^{-1} . Semi-diurnal baroclinic tides, which are generated by tide-topography interaction, represent the most energetic component of the internal wave spectrum derived from observations (Fig. 11c).

The strong baroclinic tides, and to a much lesser extent the barotropic tides, also show their imprint in glider measurements off Santo Antão and São Vicente (Fig. 11b). They are visible as undulations of the isohalines having peak-to-trough amplitudes of around 100 m and follow the same dominant tidal periods (M_2) as the velocity measurements in the spectral analysis (Fig. 11c). These internal tides can either propagate away from the coast into the open ocean or propagate onshore and dissipate in shallow waters. In fact, the observed dissipation rates of

turbulent kinetic energy, a measure of vertical mixing strength determined by microstructure measurements, are extraordinarily high above the steep slope off Santo Antão particularly below the mixed layer (Fig. 12 a, b).

Note that for the shown sections and merged profiles of turbulence dissipation rate, different tidal periods are merged together. However, highest turbulent dissipation rates are observed in the section closest to the steep slope (Fig. 12a). A comparison of the average vertical profiles of dissipation rates, color-coded by their origin, against depth reveals the intensity and spatial variation of enhanced mixing near the islands (Fig. 12b). Off Santo Antão (Fogo) mixing rates are 100 to 1000 times (10 times) higher than mixing rates determined 100 km northeast of São Vicente in the open ocean near the CVOO, with clear maxima in mixing intensity at around 100 m and 250 m depth.

Internal waves are crucial in the energy cascade from larger scales to smaller scales, making it important to analyze the energy contained within the internal wave frequency band, i.e., between the buoyancy frequency, N , and the inertial frequency, f . To this end, we calculate the power spectrum of vertical shear of horizontal velocity along the cruise tracks within the CVA from shipboard velocity data taken between 150 and 535 m (see also Section 2.3.1). The color shading in Fig. 12c marks multiples of the Garrett-Munk spectrum, the so-called Garrett-Munk level R_{gm} , where 1 corresponds to the canonically adopted background level of internal waves energy in the open ocean. In regions of strong forcing, the local internal wave spectrum is expected to deviate from the Garrett-Munk spectrum (Garrett and Munk, 1972, 1975; Cairns and Williams, 1976; Munk, 1981). East of the CVA (excluding the two seamounts), the canonical internal wave spectrum is observed (around $R_{\text{gm}} \approx 1$), whereas within the CVA, R_{gm} is closer to 2, with several hotspots ($R_{\text{gm}} \gg 2$) near or between islands. Most enhanced internal wave energy levels are evident south of Santo Antão, but particularly northeast of São Vicente and east of Maio (Fig. 12c). In accordance with results from our microstructure measurements, there is only slightly enhanced internal wave activity south of Fogo.

Fig. 11. a) Time series of meridional velocity as function of depth in the vicinity of the island Santo Antão from vmADCP measurements (the corresponding cruise track south of Santo Antão is drawn in red in Fig. 2b). b) Time series of salinity measured by a glider south of Santo Antão (brown track in Fig. 2b south of Santo Antão). Blue line marks the depth of the isopycnal 1026 kg m^{-3} . c) Spectra of the meridional velocity vertically averaged between 18 m and 100 m depth as derived from vmADCP data in red and of the vertical displacement of the 1026 kg m^{-3} isopycnal derived from the glider section shown in b) in blue, as well as eleven other glider CTD measurements in the area in grey (tracks of the gliders shown by brown lines in Fig. 2b). The vertical blue dashed line marks the depth averaged buoyancy frequency, N . d) Spectrum of the meridional velocity from a) as function of depth. The vertical dashed lines, in both c) and d), mark the main tides, K1, M2 and M3 (black) and the inertial frequency, f (green). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 12. a) Dissipation rate of turbulent kinetic energy as function of depth and distance to the coast of Santo Antão, mixed layer is shaded in grey. b) Average profiles of dissipation rates of turbulent kinetic energy near Santo Antão (blue), near Fogo (green), and at CVOO which is 100 km northeast of São Vicente in the open ocean (orange). c) Ratio of averaged vertical shear spectra from velocity data taken by vmADCPs along cruise tracks within the CVA and similarly integrated Garrett-Munk spectra. The color shading marks multiples of the Garrett-Munk spectrum. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.3. Discussion of the main physical processes contributing to biological productivity within the CVA

The three physical processes – *wind-forced island wakes*, *interactions of remotely generated mesoscale eddies with the CVA*, and *interactions of tidal flows and internal waves with the CVA* – are regionally associated with different parts of the CVA and are likely responsible for the majority of the increased vertical exchange through vertical advection and mixing in our observational datasets. Consequently, they affect the nitrate availability in the euphotic zone, thereby enhancing primary production, particularly at distinct hotspots within the CVA. Quantitatively assessing the importance of each individual process for the enhanced CHL concentrations within the CVA is challenging with the available observational dataset, which, although extensive, is insufficient to comprehensively capture the large temporal and spatial variability of the vertical exchange processes. Dedicated process studies will be necessary in the future to address this. However, for the first time in the CVA, we can identify and describe key processes affecting the enhanced biological productivity using observational data and combine these findings with theoretical insights to formulate the most comprehensive description of the physical processes involved and their relative importance.

Remote mechanisms responsible for increased CHL concentrations within the CVA

Based on the observational data taken in the CVA, we conclude that it is not likely that productivity is determined by lateral advection of biomass from the coastal upwelling area off West Africa. Rather, we agree with Cardoso et al. (2020) who hypothesized based on satellite data: that a combination of both remote and local mechanisms is probably the most accurate way of characterizing the archipelago's biological realm. A remote mechanism possibly important in the CVA is the nitrate injection (advection) below the surface by mesoscale eddies that are generated close to the African coast. It has been shown several times that mesoscale eddies transport oxygen-poor and nitrate-rich waters from the West African coastal region westward into the nitrate-depleted open Atlantic (Alpers et al., 2013; G. Fischer et al., 2016; Karstensen et al., 2015; Karstensen et al., 2017; Löscher et al., 2015). Based on glider measurements within eddies near the archipelago, an average nitrate content of $26.5 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ can be derived between 100 m and 400 m depth (Fiedler et al., 2016; Karstensen et al., 2017). From all the nitrate measurements in the CVA within the same depth range, an average background nitrate content of $20.1 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ was observed. An average eddy radius in the ETNA is 55 km (Schütte et al., 2016a) and the

CVA spans approximately 320 km by 320 km. Thus, it can be concluded that one eddy increases the nitrate content of the CVA by about 3 %, assuming that it completely dissipates within the archipelago. Although we assume that complete disintegration rarely occurs, given that approximately 12 eddies per year interact with the CVA (Cardoso et al., 2020; Schütte et al., 2016a), the lateral transport of nitrate into the CVA can be considered relevant. However, it remains unclear whether this additional nitrate supply by lateral eddy advection in deeper layers is a significant factor for the increased productivity. Clearly the nitrate have to be brought up into the euphotic zone by vertical exchange processes as vertical advection and mixing as discussed above. At the very least, it increases the nitrate gradient between surface water and depth, on which the above-mentioned processes act.

Aside from nitrate supply, the regional interactions between mesoscale eddies and the topography of the CVA are of importance for the dynamics of the ETNA. As already demonstrated by Cardoso et al. (2020) using satellite data, the interaction of the larger remotely forced open ocean eddies with the CVA influences the eddy field on a broad scale, which has in turn significant consequences for the archipelago itself. For the first time, we can support various concepts of eddy-island interactions (section 3.2.2) with observations in the CVA. Cardoso et al. (2020) observed an eddy colliding with the eastern islands Boa Vista and Maio via satellite data. They observed a filament detaching from the eddy and flowing counterclockwise along the northern side of the leeward islands, creating a cyclonic eddy. According to the theoretical work of Andres and Cenedese (2013), this type of eddy is determined by the conservation of circular momentum around the islands, which in turn could lead to a jet-like flow between the island passage and the generation of other eddies downstream (Cenedese et al., 2005). This process is in general agreement with our observations, including the example shown where a cyclonic eddy was likely formed within the archipelago after a frontal collision of a remotely forced anticyclonic eddy with the eastern islands of the CVA. Most investigations about the interaction between eddies and islands have primarily relied on laboratory experiments (Adduce & Cenedese, 2004; Andres & Cenedese, 2013; Cenedese, 2002; Cenedese et al., 2005; Tanabe & Cenedese, 2008) and numerical modeling (Simmons & Nof, 2000; Stern, 2000). From these studies, the importance of the relation between eddy radius and obstacle size has been inferred. Empirical case studies exploring this relation in situ are notably rare (Chang et al., 2012). However, due to the relatively flat topography between the eastern islands, the obstacle for the eddies in the CVA is relatively large. Indeed, Cardoso et al. (2020) demonstrated that, based on satellite derived far-field eddy trajectories,

the CVA seems to act as a highly efficient barrier for eddies, as no far-field eddy trajectory is observed to traverse the islands. Consequently, most of these eddies undergo complex transformation processes when encountering the CVA. This can be confirmed by our observations. It does not necessarily have to involve a frontal collision with the archipelago; even slight contact of the eddy rim with the island topography, as demonstrated above, can strongly affect the local island environment. For both cases (frontal collision or brief contact), it must be noted that the increased upward nitrate flux can either be caused by interaction-induced enhanced vertical advection or mixing through the eddy-induced currents along bathymetry. Furthermore, the colliding eddy could transport nitrate-rich waters into a region of enhanced mixing, thereby altering the nitrate gradient. One cyclone (Fig. 10) exhibited significantly increased mixing rates when propagating in the vicinity of the islands – without being in direct contact with the topography of the CVA. The reasons for the high mixing in these nearby eddies (up to 10 times larger than observed in eddies farther offshore) can be manifold; one explanation can be interactions with processes caused by the islands – such as the modification by the wind curl in the lee of the islands or the generally amplified internal wave field (e.g., due tide-topography interaction). It is known that mesoscale eddies modify the internal wave field (Kunze, 1985; Voet et al., 2024). The interactions between internal waves and the eddy velocity field can, for instance, lead to enhanced vertical mixing at the eddy rim where the geostrophic shear is high (Karstensen et al., 2017). Increased internal wave energy was also observed in the cyclone presented above, south of Fogo (process not shown).

All interactions between remotely generated eddies and the CVA (whether they are caused by flow-topography interactions, wind perturbations, eddy interactions with internal tides and waves or otherwise) ultimately lead to an energy transfer towards smaller scales. This energy is available for locally enhancing vertical advection or mixing, thus strengthening the upward nitrate flux (from the nitrate-rich eddy core) towards the euphotic zone and causing CHL blooms. All these distinct processes underscore the complex interplay between physical ocean dynamics and biological productivity and emphasize the importance of eddies in marine ecosystems like the CVA.

Local processes responsible for the increased CHL concentrations within the CVA

Traditionally, as outlined in the introduction, the enhanced biological productivity around islands is primarily attributed to five local processes: interactions of islands with the large-scale circulation, wind, geostrophic flow pattern, tides, and freshwater runoff (e.g. Doty & Oguri, 1956). However, in the CVA, there is no strong coherent large-scale circulation (section 3.1) or significant freshwater runoff. Additionally, seabird or seal colonies, which can locally contribute to nutrient input, are not significantly present. As discussed above, the interaction between the CVA and the geostrophic flow of remotely forced mesoscale eddies contributes to region's productivity. The remaining factors, wind and tidal forcing, also played an important role in our observations as local contributors to the elevated vertical advection and mixing in this region.

Firstly, the interaction of the CVA with the stable and relatively strong trade winds. Wind perturbations, caused by the presence of topographic obstacles like the high mountains on Fogo and Santo Antão, generate surface intensified eddies in the lee of these islands, known as island wakes (section 3.2.1). These eddies are typically characterized by intense CHL blooms. On average, island wakes are formed in the lee of Fogo are twice as numerous, stronger, and more productive than those of Santo Antão, likely due to Fogo's higher topographic elevation, which presents a greater obstacle to the wind. What likely happens southwest of Fogo and Santo Antão is similar to what Basterretxea et al. (2002) and Sangrà et al. (2007) observed in the lee of the Canary Islands: On the right/left side of the wake, wind shear produces convergence/divergence of Ekman transport, which leads to downwelling/upwelling due to negative/positive wind curl. In general, this is observed in our oceanic

datasets: atmospheric-forced moving eddy chains off Fogo and Santo Antão, are identified during several research cruises and also visible in satellite data. Although not well captured in our observational data (probably because our measurements were not close enough to or at the right position of the islands), local wind-induced coastal upwelling likely plays a role for the CHL content around the CVA. It was recently shown in a model study by Kämpf (2024) that island wakes can expel these patches of upwelled water, including their nitrate and phytoplankton loads, into the surrounding ocean.

Secondly, the interaction of the CVA with tidal flows. Tides are an energetic component of the ocean system that, as shown in section 3.2.3, can lead to enhanced vertical mixing at local hotspots. The bathymetry plays a decisive role here. A comprehensive analysis of tide-topography interactions and the resulting internal wave field requires dedicated field studies (possibly in conjunction with high-resolution modelling) and is not possible with the available opportunistic data. However, our velocity measurements and the fact that the observed internal wave field, which is usually dominated by the M2 tide, is more energetic in the immediate vicinity of islands, strongly suggest to consider tide-topography interaction in oceanographic studies of the CVA. At the Hawaiian Ridge (with a comparably tall and steep topography as the CVA), it is estimated that about 85 % of the energy contained in internal waves that are produced by tide-topography interaction propagates away into the deep ocean, while 15 % of the energy is dissipated near the generation site (Carter et al., 2008; Klymak et al., 2008). We can contribute to this discussion by showing that there are strong internal tides in the CVA, some of which also lead to strong vertical mixing hotspots. The values of observed dissipation rate of turbulent kinetic energy in the bay off Santo Antão (around $10^{-5} \text{ W kg}^{-1}$) are among the largest so far recorded in the tropical Atlantic beneath the thermocline. In addition, we hypothesize that internal tides also interact with passing mesoscale eddies in the vicinity of the CVA. Both of these local processes (wind and tides) have been shown to play an important role for the CHL distribution of the CVA and must be carefully considered in future studies.

Seasonality of CHL concentrations within the CVA

Unlike the coastal upwelling area off Northwest Africa, the seasonality of the large-scale background wind stress curl plays no significant role for the CVA. It is most strongly positive (i.e., cyclonic and upwelling) during the boreal summer, yet no increased CHL concentrations are observed in the CVA at that time (supplementary materials Fig. S2). The CHL concentration within the CVA and beyond reach its peak from January to February. This coincides with the coldest surface temperatures and the strongest winds. Both factors (enhanced wind and buoyancy loss during the boreal winter) result in the deepest mixed layer depths occurring in January and February (Fig. 13b). During that time the mixed layer occasionally extends beyond the seasonal nitracline, allowing nitrate to be readily mixed upward (Fig. 13b). This leads to a large-scale seasonality of CHL concentrations throughout the region not only confined specifically to the CVA (Fig. 13c). However, on top of the described large scale CHL seasonality, the island effects characterized in this study have a strongly amplifying effect. These result in significantly elevated absolute CHL values within the CVA specifically in boreal winter (Fig. 13c). Moreover, though CHL concentrations within the CVA are elevated nearly throughout the rest of the year, when the generally shallower mixed layers also outside of the CVA result in only background CHL concentrations in the absence of island effects (Fig. 13c).

In addition, the island-related processes themselves are subject to a seasonal cycle. The strong wind in boreal spring locally generates much more shallow and highly productive island wakes in lee of the islands. However, there is also a strong seasonality in eddy generation off the coast of West Africa, peaking in June/July (Schütte et al., 2016a). These eddies reach the CVA during boreal winter, coinciding with the peak in productivity. Vertical advection and mixing, which results from tide-topography interactions, might be relatively constant in the tropical ocean, although its dependence on stratification could introduce small

Fig. 13. a) Geographical region over which the Hovmöller diagram (c) was generated. The red lines mark the northern and southern borders of the archipelago. b) Climatological seasonal cycle of density and mixed layer depth 10–90 % percentile (grey dashed area) from all CTD stations (a total 372) available within the CVA. The red line represents the 25.6 kg m^{-3} isopycnal, which can serve as a proxy for the nitracline (for more information on the nutrient proxy or the mixed layer depth, see [supplementary materials Fig. S5](#)). The black dashed lines mark the onset and end of the overlap between the nitracline and the mixed layer, and the red arrows indicate the possible upward nitrate flux. c) Hovmöller diagram of the latitudinal (between 22°W to 26°W) averaged climatological CHL distribution. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

seasonal variations. The resulting upward nitrate flux, however, still significantly depends on the nitracline depth (Körner et al., 2024).

Thus, all described and observed processes have their greatest potential for an increased vertical nitrate flux and in consequence enhanced CHL concentrations in boreal winter/spring. The relative importance of the individual physical processes is open for further investigation and it remains a complex interplay of many different factors and processes – however, together they lead to significant local hotspots of primary production in the CVA which in turn have a substantial impact on the ecosystem.

4. Implications of the regional CHL blooms for biogeochemical properties and the CVA ecosystem

In the following, we will examine the implications of local CHL hotspots on the ecosystem of the CVA. Our goal is to investigate whether and how local physical processes and the corresponding hotspots of primary production influence the composition of organisms, possibly leading to high abundance and diversity of life forms in the ocean around the CVA.

4.1. Distribution and abundance of meso- and macrozooplankton in the CVA

The direct effects of the described physical processes on plankton organisms, such as meso- and macrozooplankton, are difficult to prove. However, in our observations, the regions with observed high biomass typically correspond quite well to the described areas of enhanced nitrate flux by vertical advection and mixing (compare for example Fig. 12c and 14a). Furthermore, the composition of organisms is

spatially diverse and seemingly structured by the different physical processes as discussed in the following.

Considerable spatiotemporal variability was found in integrated biomass distribution of copepod primary consumers when pooling data from several research cruises (Fig. 14a). Lowest biomass was generally observed south of 9°N as well as north of 17°N . However, some stations near the islands, such as in the lee of Santo Antão, also featured low copepod biomass, while offshore stations showed sporadically high copepod biomass, particularly within mesoscale eddies. In general, a positive correlation between station-integrated CHL and copepod biomass was found, indicating that enhanced primary productivity induced by various physical drivers of vertical nitrate flux directly results in elevated biomass at the primary consumer level (Fig. 14b). Note that the multinet is a slowly towed plankton net with a much smaller opening than nets typical for micronekton catches (ie. MOCNESS, RMT8, etc.), and therefore mesopelagics with a fast escape respond are not quantitatively captured. However, the dataset is internally consistent.

Examining individual stations in direct connection with the underlying physical processes reveals the following picture: The stations sampled close to Fogo (during strong wind and peak productivity season of the CVA in boreal winter), in the island wake chain (see section 3.2.1) as well as in possible remnants of a mesoscale eddy after the collision with the eastern islands (see section 3.2.2) northwest of Fogo exhibited significantly higher biomass of calanoid copepods (2- to 3-fold), euphausiids, salps, doliolids and annelids (Fig. 15) than the background waters. This pattern is reflected also in the abundance of mesopelagic fishes (total length: $< 0.2 \text{ m}$). In the lee of Santo Antão and Fogo as well as in a cyclonic eddy within the island wake chain, the abundance of mesopelagic fishes was increased by a factor of 3 to 10 relative to our open ocean reference station at the CVOO (Fig. 15). The main

Fig. 14. a) Integrated biomass (mg m^{-2} , upper 200 m) of copepods in the Cape Verde region, observed during 10 different cruises and b) relationship (linear regression with $r^2 = 0.44$, $p < 0.0001$) between integrated copepod biomass and vertically integrated CHL at the same station (CTD profile).

Fig. 15. Spatial distribution of integrated abundance (individuals per m^2 , upper 1000 m) of different taxonomic groups (A: Fishes, B: Crustaceans, C: Tunicates) from Multinet Maxi hauls. For CVOO, Fogo, and the Santo Antão onshore station, the mean of a day/night haul pair was used; the Santo Antão offshore station as well as the cyclonic eddy between the islands was only sampled once.

contributors were gonostomatid (in particular the genus *Cyclothone*) and myctophid fishes as well as the oceanic lightfish *Vinciguerria nimbaria* (Phosichthyidae), which was particularly abundant off Santo Antão. Likewise, the abundance of crustacean zooplankton, in particular of large copepods, euphausiids, decapods, and amphipods was generally increased in the near-island stations where high mixing due to internal tides was observed. While for fishes and crustaceans, the relative composition remained roughly similar across stations, pelagic tunicates varied in their relative importance, with salps, doliolids and appendicularians dominating more offshore at the CVOO. Off Santo Antão, doliolids dominated in terms of abundance (with pyrosomes dominating biomass-wise due to their large individual size). Doliolids were almost absent in the remnants of the mesoscale eddy and off Fogo, where salps, appendicularians, and pyrosomes were dominant. Off CVOO, pyrosomes were absent both in the net samples and in in-situ video observations.

When the biological data are roughly assigned to the different local physical processes, an increased abundance associated with island-related physical features is evident. Additionally, the abundances of key zooplankton and micronekton taxa vary across the different physical regimes, reflecting the influence of these processes on biomass distribution. Generally, it has to be noted that for the “pelagic tunicates” group (Fig. 15), individual abundance may not represent biomass contribution due to their wide range in sizes (from < 0.01 m to > 0.2 m).

The different physical processes, albeit infrequent, yet characterized by intense vertical advection or mixing, have demonstrated considerable potential in elucidating poorly known biological and biogeochemical phenomena. Previous studies of oxygen depleted eddies in the tropical Atlantic have shown that the passage of an eddy can affect zooplankton vertical migration (Hausse et al., 2016; Karstensen et al., 2015). At the same time elevated surface mesozooplankton biomass as well as particle

export flux into the deep ocean was observed associated to the passage of an oxygen depleted eddy (Hauss et al. 2016, Fiedler et al. 2016). In such eddies, the zooplankton community structure was observed to shift towards hypoxia-tolerant species (Christiansen et al., 2018), which can also result in decreased downward carbon flux due to midwater interception if these organisms are flux feeding and become highly abundant (Christiansen et al., 2018; Stenvers et al., 2021).

Zooplankton and micronekton are intermediate food web links between primary producers and predators (e.g., fishes, cephalopods, seabirds and cetaceans). They also act as “gatekeepers” of the biological pump (Kiko et al., 2020) by influencing the export of organic carbon and nitrogen from the euphotic, climate-active zone to the ocean interior, but also supplying most of the organic matter for the ocean midwater and benthic food webs. Accordingly, physical forcing which may induce changes in the species composition and biomass of zooplankton, as well as behavior of individual species, directly impact vertical biogeochemical fluxes, and ultimately seafloor communities. Investigating the exact trophic pathways in midwater food webs via stomach content analysis and dietary tracers, including detritivores, planktivores and predators, will elucidate the fate of the CHL and the effect on the deep pelagic ecosystem.

4.2. Distribution and abundance of higher trophic levels in the CVA

It is expected that increased biomass of meso- and microzooplankton should also result in increased biomass of organisms at higher trophic levels. Direct quantification of these typically large fauna remains difficult as they are highly mobile. As an indirect indication of biomass of higher trophic levels, we here analyzed: 1) the annual fish catches that are landed in tons on the Cape Verde islands, see (IMar, 2023) and 2) the annual abundances of humpback whales observed in close proximity to the CVA (determined by capture/recapture using fluke photography data from Wenzel et al. 2020). Both fish landings and humpback whale abundance show remarkable parallels with the average annual CHL concentration across the CVA (Fig. 16a).

In the early 2000 s, the fish landings were around 8,500 t, and almost doubled to over 15,000 t in the following years. CHL concentrations paralleled this pattern. In the following, we take a more detailed look at the numbers concerning the landed fish catch in Cape Verde, dividing it into three categories: small pelagic fish, larger predators like tuna and other species. There was a highly significant ($p < 0.0001$) positive relationship between tuna landings (Fig. 16b), comprising mainly yellowfin (*Thunnus albacares*), skipjack (*Katsuwonus pelamis*), Judeu – frigate tuna (*Auxis thazard*), and Serra – Wahoo (*Acanthocybium solandri*) and the annual mean CHL concentrations within the CVA. The fact that all of these species are predators suggests that the primary productivity signal propagates up within the food web. However, landings of zooplanktivorous small pelagic fish species (mackerel scad (*Decapterus macarellus*) and Chicharro-Bigeye scad (*Selar crumenophthalmus*)), were negatively correlated to annual mean CHL values in the region (Fig. 16c). This negative relationship was weaker but indicates that there is at least no direct positive impact of high annual CHL on landings of these species, while again for all others combines (including demersal perciform fishes as well as sharks) there is again a positive relationship to CHL ($p < 0.05$). Food web effects may thus outweigh direct aggregation effects on some species.

As there is no apparent time lag but a direct correlation between the annual values of CHL and some species groups (e.g. tuna, which are predatory), this can probably not be explained by an increase in recruitment in these species. Rather, we assume a whale and fish aggregation effect in years with beneficial feeding conditions around the islands. This supports the idea that localized physical drivers - by enhancing nutrient concentrations in the mixed layer - trigger CHL blooms around the islands, which in turn create favorable feeding conditions and attract higher trophic levels, contributing to the observed aggregations of fish and marine megafauna. However more recently, the reported landings have sharply declined and become decoupled from the CHL trend. The decoupling can be due to other effects such as overfishing or landing/reporting in other countries as only landings in Cape Verde are considered here. The annual sightings of Humpback whales

Fig. 16. a) CHL averaged over the CVA (14.5° n to 17.5° n and 16° w to 22.5° w) (green), annual total fish catch in metric tons (t) within the 12 nautical mile zone around the Cape Verde islands (blue, IMar, 2023) and abundance estimate of humpback whales per year within the CVA (red, from Wenzel et al., 2020). Correlation between the average CHL around the islands and annual catch of b) tuna species, c) small pelagics and d) other species. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

can be influenced by numerous factors; however, it was observed to significantly increase from 2010 to 2015 followed by a decrease in sightings in subsequent years, mirroring the overall CHL concentration trends in the CVA. Again, the abundance of this long-lived and migratory species around the islands rather reflects an attraction mechanism rather than a direct productivity/growth of higher trophic levels.

Although consistent time series observations on top predators such as sharks, blue marlin and toothed whales are lacking, their habitat use around the islands (including nurseries) (Hazevoet et al., 2010; Rosa et al., 2023) indicates that the enhanced biological productivity plays a critical role in provisioning the entire pelagic ecosystem in this region. Consequently, it becomes evident that the physical processes around the CVA play a significant role in steering and structuring pelagic ecosystems.

5. Summary and conclusion

This manuscript investigates the local ecosystem of the CVA in detail across disciplines, from the physical basis to the impact on biology. We hypothesize that small-scale local physical processes around the islands lead to an increased nitrate flux into the mixed layer, which promotes regional CHL blooms and ultimately support a rich and diverse ecosystem. The CVA region can be viewed as a testbed in order to improve the understanding of the ecosystem forcing by physical small-scale motions through their impact on the vertical nutrient flux, which are equally important in other vast areas of the world ocean.

Primary production around the CVA is seasonal, peaking in February, which contrast with the seasonality of the Northwest African coastal upwelling system, where peak production occurs in May. This suggests that direct advection of biomass from the coastal upwelling area to the CVA does not play a major role, while local processes primarily shape primary production in the CVA. The objective of this study was therefore to identify the key forcing mechanisms driving regional CHL blooms within the CVA.

The upper Atlantic is nitrate-deficient. Vertical nitrate fluxes are generally driven by vertical advection and mixing (which require a nitrate gradient to be effective). These vertical exchange processes can primarily be forced by the interaction of the island topography with wind, large-scale ocean circulation, tides and mesoscale eddies. The wind within the CVA is relatively strong and steady all year round with a moderate seasonality (maximum speed in boreal winter). The large-scale ocean circulation around the CVA is dominated by alternating zonal jets. They are disturbed by the CVA, resulting in a more complex flow field around the archipelago. However, the low-frequency large scale circulation is characterized by a rather weak and sluggish flow. Enhanced potential for vertical advection and mixing in the upper ocean is associated with high-frequency ocean dynamics, such as tides or mesoscale eddies. In examining our diverse observational datasets from the past 20 years within the CVA with that regard, three main physical processes emerge that contribute to enhanced vertical advection and mixing: Firstly, the high topography of Fogo and Santo Antão leads to wind disturbances, which can generate productive oceanic island wakes (more pronounced in the lee of Fogo than of Santo Antão). Secondly, remotely generated nitrate-rich mesoscale eddies propagate toward the CVA and can either directly interact with the topography of the islands and seamounts or they can interact with processes triggered by the island's presence (such as the wind curl in the lee or the enhanced internal wave field induced by tide-topography interactions). We observed about 10 times more mixing in eddies interacting with the islands or island triggered processes than in eddies further away from the archipelago. This represents a transfer of energy from the mesoscale to the submesoscale down to small, dissipative scales. Thirdly, enhanced vertical mixing induced by tide-topography interaction is observed within the CVA. In the spatially restricted hotspots, up to 1000 times more mixing has been measured compared to stations outside the CVA. Although the observations of turbulent kinetic energy are extensive to

some extent, they remain too sparse to systematically investigate tidally induced mixing around the CVA. However, numerous shipboard velocity measurements show that the energy of the internal wave field is significantly higher (including intense hotspots) within the archipelago compared to the background internal wave field outside the archipelago and can be regarded as an indicator of elevated mixing activity.

These spatially defined physical drivers of regional CHL blooms have been combined with the biological dataset from the past 20 years in the CVA. This approach has provided insights that help explaining the relatively complex biological context around the CVA. In general, it was anticipated that a correlation exists between the regional blooms of CHL and zooplankton biomass – and was indeed observed. However, we hypothesize that differences in the abundance of certain zooplankton taxa are associated with the various physical processes, which likely influence secondary production and trophic transfer. The specific regional distribution of physical processes could play a key role in shaping the composition of ecological communities of the CVA, which in turn modulate carbon flux or oxygen consumption or impact the marine ecosystems. It is remarkable that the abundance of mesopelagic fishes increased by a factor of 3 to 10 in areas where elevated vertical advection or mixing was detected, compared to our open ocean reference station at the CVOO. Moving further up the food chain, we found a positive correlation between the annual CHL concentrations in the CVA and the annual fish catch of small pelagic fish, as well as the fish catch of larger predators like tuna. Even the abundance of humpback whales showed a positive correlation with mean annual CHL concentrations in the CVA. We attribute this to an aggregation effect of whales and larger fish in years with favorable feeding conditions around the islands, rather than a direct increase in productivity or growth of higher trophic levels.

These observations indicate that bottom-up effects of the diverse physical drivers appear to cascade through the food chain and exert a transient shaping effect on the ecosystem and supports our central hypothesis that small-scale local physical processes around the islands lead to an increased nutrient flux into the mixed layer, which promotes regional CHL blooms and ultimately support a rich and diverse ecosystem (Fig. 17). It follows that various physical processes generate distinct environments at different scales, potentially providing ecological niches that support a wide range of species, including those that might otherwise be outcompeted in more homogenous conditions. This environmental heterogeneity created by mesoscale and submesoscale features may thus help explain the longstanding 'paradox of the plankton' (Bracco et al., 2000).

The observed interplay between ocean dynamics, topography and biology enhances our understanding of the functionality of the CVA ecosystem. It also calls for more research with an interdisciplinary, observatory approach to unravel for example the impact of enhanced productivity on deep-water benthic ecosystems via benthopelagic coupling. Also dedicated measurements should show how the CVA is utilized as foraging grounds by organisms from higher trophic levels such as cetaceans and elasmobranchs. The knowledge can be used for future monitoring efforts that take into account these interdisciplinary interactions to support decision-making for sustainable management of the marine ecosystem of CVA. It calls for augmenting current approaches for fisheries monitoring (mainly based on landing statistics) by a more multidisciplinary approach that involves in-situ surveys for physical and chemical oceanography and marine ecology (covering different trophic levels) combined with high-resolution satellite-based observations. The basic physical drivers need to be better localized and understood, which can lead to an improved prediction tool for the productivity of the CVA. With this interdisciplinary approach, covering the full range of processes and parameters from physical small-scale vertical advection and mixing to the abundance of large predators, we aim to contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the CVA marine environment, which is also a prerequisite for having a digital representation either in terms of coupled physical-biogeochemical-ecosystem models or ultimately a digital twin of the ocean (Bronner et al., 2023). In particular,

Fig. 17. Schematic of the three primary physical forcing mechanisms for regional CHL blooms in twenty years of observational data within the CVA: (A) Island wakes generated by wind distortions due to the island's topography, (B) tide-topography interactions, and (C) remotely generated nutrient-rich mesoscale eddies propagating toward the CVA and interacting with the topography of islands and seamounts. All three processes induce vertical advection and mixing, facilitating vertical nutrient transport (shown in yellow) into the mixed layer, where regional CHL blooms develop (shown in green). The zoomed-in areas, indicated by circles, highlight the indications of larger and more diverse biological communities near these processes compared to the oligotrophic open ocean (D). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

understanding biological diversity, biological standing stocks, biogeochemical fluxes and their various interactions with physical processes is crucial for ongoing efforts to protect and sustainably utilize the marine environment - not only in the CVA, but also on a global scale.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Florian Schütte: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anna Christina Hans:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Marco Schulz:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Rebecca Hummels:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Olivier Assokpa:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Data curation. **Peter Brandt:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Conceptualization; Funding acquisition. **Rainer Kiko:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Arne Körtzinger:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Björn Fiedler:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Funding acquisition. **Tim Fischer:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology. **Elizandro Rodrigues:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Henk-Jan Hoving:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Helena Hauss:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocan.2025.103479>.

Data availability

The assembled shipboard measurements (27 research cruises), glider data and fish catch data used in this paper are available and collected at <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.980861>. For more information on the biological Data on fish catch see (IMar, 2023). The Annual Humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*) abundance (2011–2017) was used from published data (Wenzel et al., 2020). The used satellite altimetry data can be downloaded at <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00148>. Chlorophyll concentrations used in the manuscript are derived from ocean colour observations with spectroradiometers and provided by Marine Copernicus (<https://marine.copernicus.eu>). The datasets used include the 4 km x 4 km resolution daily data (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00282>) and the interpolated daily cloud-free version of chlorophyll also at 4 km x 4 km resolution (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00281>). The used Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform (CCMP) 6-hourly wind dataset is produced by Remote Sensing Systems and available for the period from Jan 01, 1992 to Dec 31, 2019.

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